

TECHNISCHE
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Data management plan (DMP)

[Country Innovation Index Analysis]

[CIA DMP]

[coverspace]

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1.0	2022-05-01	First version of DMP – created for start of project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
GII	Global Innovation Index
EIS	European Innovation Scoreboard
OED	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
BII	Bloomberg Innovation Index
CIIA	Country Innovation Index Analysis

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf

1. Data description

1a Lists of data sets that will be reused or produced

Produced data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	OUTPUT.csv	standard office documents	CSV	<100 MB	no

Reused data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	DOI and license / source	contains sensitive data
R1	Global Innovation Index (GII): 2013 - 2021	standard office documents	CSV	Indicator Rankings & Analysis Global Innovation Index	no
R2	Bloomberg Innovation Index (BII): 2016 - 2021	standard office documents	CSV	BII- (europa.eu)	no
R3	European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS): 2014 - 2021	standard office documents	xls	European innovation scoreboard European Commission (europa.eu)	no
R4	OECD Business Innovation Statistics: 2013 - 2019	standard office documents	CSV	Business innovation statistics and indicators - OECD	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Data generation

All datasets have been merged and preprocessed. Initially standardized for consistency with regard to data types, indexes, naming conventions as well as column groups before merging them altogether in one dataset for coherent querying later on. The original datasets are saved as csv files in folders (./data/gii), (./data/oecd), (./data/bii) and (./data/eis), where the merged and preprocessed dataset is saved in (./OUTPUT.csv). The output csv and images files will be created by running the source code. The programming language Python and Jupyter notebooks will be used in this experiment for data processing. The final code will be uploaded to the github as well as on Zenodo. The total size of the above-mentioned data will not exceed 10 MB in size, which should be easily handleable by machines for both execution and storage. The source code will be under github version control during

creation and stored in a public github repository at https://github.com/samahjaber/DataStewardship_DMP_CIIA. In this repository, pre-existing dataset is stored in the "data", the source code for the processing of data can be found in the "code" directory. Documentation can be found in the README.md file as well as in the "Innovation Indices.ipynb" and the license for reusing the source code in the "LICENCE" file. Output file from running the source code are stored in a "OUTPUT.csv".

Data reuse

The GitHub repository containing the data, the source code and the result dataset will be publicly available in: https://github.com/samahjaber/DataStewardship_DMP_CIIA
This DMP has the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6510184.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The source code will be under github version control during creation and stored in a public github repository at https://github.com/samahjaber/DataStewardship_DMP_CIIA.

Fill all possible metadata provided by Zenodo, which are: publication date, title, authors, description, where will be mentioned the abstract of the project, basic data description and license, version, language, keywords, license and contact person with ORCID. Zenodo will automatically create DOI. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

For example: will add controlled vocabularies (ISO-3166 standards):

<https://github.com/lukes/ISO-3166-Countries-with-Regional-Codes/blob/master/all/all.xml>

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g. checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

The data will be stored on a local machine for manipulation and in a GitHub repository for Version Control.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this change, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to the data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only
R4	reading only	reading only	reading only
P1	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (<https://www.tuwien.at/en/research/rti-support/research-ethics/>). They are described in detail in separate documents. The research has not been reviewed yet by any ethics committee.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns. Further data will be made available with restrictive access.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
R1	Open			GitHub		CC BY-NC-SA

R2	Open			GitHub		CC BY-NC-SA
R3	Open			GitHub		CC BY-NC-SA
R4	Open			GitHub		CC BY-NC-SA
P1	Open			GitHub		CC BY

The repository used in this project described in the following paragraph.

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

In order to produce the output data and visualization files, following tools and libraries are necessary:

- Python 3.7.3
- jupyter Notebook 6.0.2
- pandas 0.25.3
- numpy 1.17.4
- scikit-learn 0.22
- matplotlib 3.1.1
- seaborn 0.9.0

Description of protocol to access restricted data:

5b Long-term preservation and reusability

The whole project can be found in the repository described above, which is entirely managed by the author, accordingly data is planned to be preserved indefinitely. There are no relevant costs for long term preservation.

dataset ID	location for long-term storage (min. 10 years)	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	GitHub		Decision makers in industry Members of the scientific community
P2	GitHub		Decision makers in industry Members of the scientific community
P3	GitHub		Decision makers in industry Members of the scientific community
P4	GitHub		Decision makers in industry Members of the scientific community
R1	GitHub		Decision makers in industry Members of the scientific community

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The principal investigator of this DMP will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Title	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0